

D2.4 – Intermediate report and risk log - Report Nr 1

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first risk report and updated risk log at month M06. The risk report and risk log is updated every 6 months and is presented in different deliverables. We report on the occurrence of foreseen and unforeseen risks, and update the table of potential risks with additional foreseen risks.

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1. Introduction

This document is the updated version of the risk log presented in deliverable D2.2 and should be considered as an incremental deliverable. The Risk Management Plan of the project dAIEDGE has been described in deliverable D2.2, and an initial risk log with the risks identified at the proposal submission time were reported there. In this document, we report on the occurrence of foreseen risks in the previous period and state the adopted mitigation measures. Then, we present an updated list of possible risks, with the new risks identified in the period M01-M06.

2. Intermediate report on risk occurrence

In this section, we report on the occurrence of previously identified risks or unforeseen risk, together with the adopted mitigation measure.

In the period M01-M06, following foreseen risks have occurred:

Table 1: Occurrence of foreseen risks in the period M01-M06

Nr	Time of occurrence	Description of risk	Adopted mitigation measure
No foreseen risk occurred in the period M01-M06			

In the period M01-M06, following unforeseen risks have occurred:

Nr	Time of occurrence	Description of risk	Adopted mitigation measure
U1	M2	<u>Bankruptcy of one partner</u> : The company NVISO SA, an associated partner in the project dAIEDGE is in situation of bankruptcy since September 7th, 2023. As an effect, NVISO SA cannot receive the planned funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). For this reason, NVISO SA has to be terminated from the project dAIEDGE	<p>Preparation of a Grant Agreement Amendment with reallocation of the tasks originally planned for NVISO SA to existing associated partners from Switzerland.</p> <p>Organisation of Steering Committee meetings to discuss the case.</p> <p>Organisation of dedicated meetings with Swiss partners to discuss the reallocation of the tasks.</p> <p>Consultation with the Project Officer to validate the procedure.</p>

			See Grant Amendment Preparation Document in Appendix 1
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3. Updated risk log

In comparison with the original list of identified risks from the proposal (D2.2), the consortium has identified 4 additional risks which will be monitored during the project.

The following table is the updated risk log at the time of the current period (version 1, M6):

Table 2: Updated risk log at M06

Nr	Description of risk	Likelihood	Severity	Risk degree	WPs	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
R1	Limited engagement or interaction with other pillars of the European AI Lighthouse	2	4	4	WP1	Most dAIEDGE partners are already active in related projects and networking associations. Dedicated communication means will be put in place (technical and organisational)
R2	Missing or insufficient expertise for delivery of roadmaps and scientific agenda	1	5	5	WP3	The consortium has been carefully assembled to bring together leading organisations with multidisciplinary skills. Input for road mapping and agenda will be collected by dedicated questionnaires, which will be distributed to other members of the NoE beyond the consortium.
R3	Incompatibility between different modules, integration risks	2	3	6	WP4	Development of a framework federation tool in WP4, based on existing assets from previous EU projects. Integration sprints, “agile” development, feedback to architecture design after unit tests
R4	Insufficient technological readiness of the additional components	3	2	6	WP5, WP6	We foresee to have two iterations for the development of technical and scientific advances, allowing to generate a Minimum Viable Product already at month 16. Demonstrator implementation

						will feed back issues to improve and correct errors for the final version
R5	Limitation to a few pilots/use-cases	1	3	3	WP5, WP6	In order to go beyond the three pilots of the project, we will work on community building and business development in WP8, which will raise interest outside of the consortium. Open calls will help pursuing additional use-cases and technical developments.
R6	Low number of proposals submitted to open calls	2	3	6	WP8	Submissions reception, periodic checking. Analysing impacts of the dissemination activities and defining new ones based on the analysis' results.
R7	Low quality of the third party projects submitted	2	4	8	WP8	Only proposals reaching the desired quality level will be selected. The non-compromised funds will be added to the next open call or will be invested in providing additional support to awarded third party projects, if there are no additional open calls.
R8	Lack of involvement of stakeholders for dissemination and exploitation objectives	1	4	4	WP7, WP8	Continuous monitoring of exploitation and dissemination activities. A first draft of the dissemination plan will be delivered early to help partners. Creation of dedicated tools (virtual incubator, incentive models) for reaching the critical mass for exploitation

Additional risks in version D2.4

R9	Difficulty to reach KPI 8 with 200 studies run over the virtual lab	3	3	9	WP4	Increased visibility and communication about the features of the virtual lab and resources federation
R10	Difficulty to reach KPI 7, aiming at more than 150 members in the network	3	3	9	WP3	Participation to ecosystem mapping, increased exploration of networks and consortia of other projects
R11	Difficulty to reach KPI 9, aiming at more than	3	3	9	WP4	Increased visibility and communication about the features of the marketplace.

	250k assets available in the marketplace					Increased cooperation with AI on Demand platform
R12	Difficulty to organise the work among the consortium due to high number of partners	2	2	4	WP2	Creation of working groups dedicated to specific topics within the work packages (organised by the WP leaders)
R13	Limitations in addressing all the possible ethical concerns and risks to Privacy and Data protection during the design stages	1	3	3	WP9	Nomination of a AI Ethical Advisor with specific expertise on data privacy and security aspect. Organisation of working sessions with the AI Ethical Advisor and partners covering specific technologies

ANNEX A: Grant Amendment Preparation Document

1. Introduction

The company NVISO SA, an associated partner in the project dAIEDGE is in situation of bankruptcy since September 7th, 2023. As an effect, NVISO SA cannot receive the planned funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). For this reason, NVISO SA has to be terminated from the project dAIEDGE.

The purpose of this document is to prepare the Grant Agreement Amendment to officially terminate the participation of the associated partner NVISO SA.

2. Rationale

- NVISO SA is in situation of bankruptcy since 07.09.2023 according to the Swiss Official Gazette of Commerce (SOGC)¹
- The representatives of NVISO SA have confirmed the bankruptcy in an online meeting on 05.10.2023, in which the Coordinator requested NVISO SA to officially notify the Coordinator of the situation of bankruptcy via e-mail.
- The Coordinator contacted the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), who confirmed that SERI will not conclude a funding contract with NVISO SA. SERI is ready to adapt the funding agreements with the remaining Swiss participants once an according Grant Agreement Amendment has been signed by the Coordinator and the PO – while keeping the total funding envelope for Swiss participants equal.
- The Coordinator contacted the Project Officer who confirmed that the Consortium can decide to terminate the participation of a partner by applying for a Grant Agreement Amendment.
- The Coordinator informed the consortium via e-mail on November 9th, 2023 that NVISO SA will be terminated, that a Grant Agreement Amendment will be necessary, and that the remaining Swiss partners of dAIEDGE will discuss how the tasks originally planned for NVISO SA can be redistributed.
- The remaining Swiss partners (AEGIS, BCA, CSEM, ETHZ and HES-SO) have been invited to a meeting on November 15th, 2023. During this meeting several options have been discussed, and a final redistribution of tasks and efforts has been adopted by all partners (see section 3). CSEM and ETHZ declared that they do not want to take over additional tasks, and the tasks have been redistributed to AEGIS, BCA and HES-SO
- After discussion with the concerned partners (AEGIS, BCA and HES-SO), a reallocation of tasks, effort in person-months and budget has been decided and agreed by all parties (see section 3).

¹ <https://www.shab.ch/#!/search/publications/detail/11648918-de5d-475e-832f-75588200d551>

- The partners taking over the tasks originally planned by NVISO SA have produced a written statement that they have the capacity to take additional tasks.

3. Proposed distribution of tasks and budget

The original involvement of NVISO SA in the project dAIEDGE is as follows: the planned effort was 26 PMs distributed on 3 work packages (WP4: 11PM, WP6: 5PM, WP8: 10PM). The total budget of NVISO is 411.250,00 EUR.

The tasks in which NVISO SA was involved and their contribution are

- T4.2 Virtual research lab design [M06-M12] NVISO will contribute its expertise as user of heterogeneous edge systems and dedicated HPC infrastructure.
- T4.3 – Scheduling optimization and ML model deployment [M06-M30] NVISO will contribute its expertise in developing applications with inference at the edge on ultra-low-power cyber-physical systems.
- T6.3 – Demonstrators evaluation and validation [M25-M36] NVISO will contribute in the validation of the demonstrator use-cases as an edge AI application development and integration company
- T8.2 – Network expansion through open calls [M8-M35] NVISO will provide a support programme for the industry-focused open calls involving AI Talents and Enterprises/SMEs.

After discussion with the Swiss partners, following redistribution is planned:

- HES-SO will take over the tasks originally planned for NVISO SA in WP4
- AEGIS will take over the tasks originally planned for NVISO SA in WP6
- BCA will take over the tasks originally planned for NVISO SA in WP8

The distribution of the budget to the partners will be done proportionally to the effort:

- WP4 (HES-SO): 5PM out of 26, corresponding to 19,23% of the budget
- WP6 (AEGIS) : 10PM out of 26, corresponding to 38,46% of the budget
- WP8 (BCA): 11PM out of 26, corresponding to 42,31% of the budget

Accordingly, the following additional budget is planned for the partners AEGIS, BCA and HES-SO:

Partner	Additional effort (PMs)	Direct Personnel costs (€)	Purchase costs				Indirect costs (€)	Total Estimated eligible costs (€)	Reimbursement rate	Financial contribution (€)
			Travel (€)	Equipment (€)	Other goods, works and services (€)	Total costs (€)				
AEGIS	7,5	60.000	2.000	1.269	0	1.269	15.817,25	79.086,25	100%	79.086,25
BCA	12,5	121.875	3.500	1.163	0	1.163	31.634,50	158.172,50	100%	158.172,50
HES-SO	16	134.880	3.000	1.312	0	1.312	34.798,00	173.990,00	100%	173.990,00
Total:	36	316.755	8.500	3.744	0	3.744	82.249,75	411.248,00	100%	411.248,00

4. Procedure

The Coordinator suggests to start a Grant Amendment procedure to confirm the termination of NVISO SA and reflect the budget and task allocation changes.

The present document will be sent to the Consortium and to the Project Officer for approval, before starting the Grand Amendment.

5. Action points

- The Coordinator will request a validation of the procedure by all the partners
- The Coordinator will contact the Project Officer to validate the procedure
- The Coordinator will follow the PO's recommendations

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